

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS BASED ON REFLECTIVITY

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Abstract

The article defines the level of psychologist professionalism in practice by examining the role that student individuality played in his study as well as personal factors in the development of professional reflection. Students' psycho-educational study environments can be improved using this analysis: to focus on psychology students' personal and professional reflection development.

Keywords

the individual aspect; professional assessment; mental activity; communication; motivation; empathy; social competence; degree of personal control; what orientation in life means.

Reflectivity is striving for maximum awareness of one's own actions, in other words, attunement to finding the meaning of the events taking place and the relationships between them. It is considered a system-forming and multifunctional personal quality that contributes to the effective assimilation, deepening and processing of social experience, switching from the external level to the internal plan. Reflectivity is also the ability of individuals and society to think critically, to see negative sides, pathological phenomena, to identify potential dangers, to make decisions and protective measures that can prevent or slow down some trends.

In order to understand the concept of reflectivity, it is necessary to clarify the meaning of the word reflection, which implies the process of individuals paying attention to themselves and to consciousness itself, then reflectivity means the ability of subjects to comprehend their personality, to understand the origins of their own actions.

Thus, reflection is a qualitative characteristic indicating that consciousness is able to direct attention inward. Reflectivity is a quantitative characteristic that demonstrates the severity of such an ability, the criticality of analysis, and depth. Reflection literally implies turning back. The concept of reflecting is used to denote the process of thinking about one's own mental state, turning attention inward. In

various sciences and philosophical views, the term in question has a different content. So Locke meant by reflection the source of specific knowledge when the action of consciousness is contemplated. Leibniz considered reflection to be the attention of individuals to what is happening inside them. According to Jung, ideas are a reflection on representations received from the outside. Generalizing all views, the common interpretation of reflection is its focus on the inner world of individuals. Reflectivity also acts as a personal trait that characterizes self-directed cognition. The analyzed phenomenon is ranked among the most important characteristics of consciousness.

Psychologists emphasize the importance of separating the two above-mentioned similar phenomena. Reflectivity in psychology is presented as a personal property, and reflection is the process of cognition of one's own personality.

At the same time, the first means the quality of personality that determines reflection as a process. Reflectivity has a criterion of expression and is determined by the aspiration of the processes of cognition into one's own personality. These two above-mentioned phenomena are realized with the help of reflexive abilities.

Thus, reflectivity is the ability to analyze one's own personality, to discover the motives of one's actions, including:

- past deeds and events;
- emotional state;
- successful or unsuccessful results of activity;
- changing personality traits, character traits.

Each individual has a different level of reflection. It is conditioned by intellectual development, the level of knowledge, education. Some subjects continuously analyze their own actions, reflect on the motivation of their actions, others - and do not think at all about their own behavior. A huge role here is given to the individual's desire to understand his own misconceptions, to realize mistakes, the level of self-criticism and the need to compare his own person with the environment.

In the psychology of education, the psychological mechanisms of students' self-development (goal formation, reflexive self-organization, interiorization, identification) are characterized. The psychological and pedagogical conditions that ensure the formation of psychological prerequisites for professional self-realization among students are highlighted: a systematic approach to the organization of the process of their psychological training; the establishment of subject-subject relations between teachers and students as the psychological basis of their productive

educational interaction; the influence of the structure of students' values; orientation to the development of their creative individuality; actualization of the need for self-realization; increasing competence in the field of psychology of professionalism. But the importance of the student's personality itself in the development of professional reflection and increasing the level of professionalism in the future is not indicated. A distinctive feature of a person in comparison with an animal is the presence of consciousness, which arises due to language (speech) and labor

(activities). Activity is an active interaction of a person with the environment, in which he achieves a consciously set goal as a result of his needs and motive. The activity must be purposeful, otherwise it can turn into impulsive unregulated behavior. Also, the activity should be productive, that is, it should have an end result.

As a result, products of the external world (technology, art, scientific work) and transformations in the person himself (knowledge, skills, abilities) can act. Depending on which changes are the main ones for the person himself, there are different types of activity: labor, cognitive, communicative, etc. For a student, the main activity is learning (cognitive activity). The products of this activity are the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during training. Of course, this does not always happen, because not all students are willing and able to study, and not just to study, but to take a really active position in the learning process, that is, to be the subject of this activity. But, along with activity, the formation of a person as a person can occur through communication and through self-development. In the field of activity, there is an expansion of the "application of man": personal choice and development of new types of activities by a person, identification of the most significant aspects of the mastered activity, subordination of all other types of activities to the main one and focusing on it. The sphere of communication is very important for a student, especially for a student studying in the field of Psychology, since the chosen profession involves the sphere of communicative interaction with other people. In the sphere of communication, there is an expansion and deepening of his connections, and later various personal changes in a person can be noted. In the sphere of communication, the formation of the image of the "I" is carried out under the influence of the inclusion of a person in different social groups. Entering into communication with each other, students pursue a specific goal: to make another person like-minded, to get recognition from him, to keep him from doing the wrong thing, to give recommendations, to advise on issues of interest, to please. All this

happens through the use of speech, expression, emotions, i.e. there is also an attempt to influence another person (the interlocutor). At the same time, describing communication as a special kind of activity, it is also necessary to see that without it, a full-fledged the development of a person as a person, as a subject of activity, and as an individual. Communication is the strongest factor involved in personality formation. But it is not only communicative, but also perceptual (perception of each other) and interactive (interaction). These aspects of communication determine the process of interaction, make students active participants in this process and determine their activities. The level of activity of a subject depends more on its properties (social intelligence, motivation, abilities), processes (thinking, memory, emotions) and states (tension, apathy). Also, communication as an activity is of great importance for the development of the emotional and volitional sphere of the student. Whether he will be persistent, determined, courageous, purposeful in the future profession of a psychologist or he will have the opposite qualities prevail – all this is to a very large extent determined by how favorable to the development of these qualities are those specific communication situations in which a student finds himself day after day in the process of studying at a university. Subsequently, this will determine his behavior in professional activity. The student's own experience, which consists of direct knowledge of people, experiences about their behavior when meeting them and his own actions in response to their behavior, is only one of the ways to form the qualities necessary for him to successfully practice as a psychologist. Another way is the constant enrichment of theoretical information related to various areas of human consciousness, penetration into all new layers of the human psyche, comprehension of the laws governing his behavior through reading literature, watching realistic films and performances; finally, it is penetration into the inner world of a person, understanding the mechanisms that ensure his existence, i.e. direct participation in the diversity of the surrounding world, represented in human life. It is then that the existing reality will determine the personal essence of a person, in our case, a student. Changes that occur with the personality in the process of preparation mastering professional activity and its independent implementation, lead to the formation of a personality as a professional specialist.

Professional reflection is considered as a criterion of professional maturity. This is a mechanism for understanding and rethinking one's professional activity and oneself as its subject in order to predict, critically analyze, reorganize, and evaluate the effectiveness of personal development. It is a constant reflection on yourself and your activities. The ability of a student studying in the field of

Psychology to analyze and evaluate his feelings, strengths and weaknesses of his personality, the degree of their compliance with professional tasks indicates about his level of development of professional reflection. Reflection makes it possible to avoid the negative consequences of stereotyping, manifested in errors of perception and understanding,

in a distorted interpretation of actions and deeds, in the formation of prejudices, which contributes to the organization of constructive psychological communication and interaction. The peculiarities of perception and understanding of the mechanisms of professionalism are indicators of the formation of the core of the professional worldview of students, future psychologists, since in this perception all cognitive and regulatory systems of a professional are manifested. Reflection is a vector of development of subjectivity, individuality, uniqueness and uniqueness of personality. The student, being a person, must take an active, purposeful, viable position in the activity that defines him as a subject. The student's personality is the bearer of this subjectivity within the framework of the development of professional reflection. At the same time, personality determines the development of reflection on practical activity (namely professional reflection). The quality and intensity of professional reflection development depend on such personal factors as: motivation, empathy, social intelligence, level of subjective control, life-meaning orientations.

Before describing the immediate personal factors and their significance in the development of professional reflection, it is necessary to clarify the concept of "personal factor" and reveal its essence. Let's start with the definition of the concept "factor: factor (English) is the one who (or what) moves, acts, creates, does (from Lat. *facere* – to do). Currently, this word is used in economic and political sciences and is most often of a commercial nature, since it has the semantic load of a certain intermediary between something and something. If the concept of "factor" is applied in psychology, then its content will already be different – it is a kind of resource or condition for something. A. R. Luria studied this concept as part of its application to psychological science (neuropsychology). In his work, the factor is interpreted as a structural unit of higher mental functions: "... various functions include a common factor, and the identification of these common factors contributes to a much deeper analysis of the structure of mental processes". A factor is the cause, the driving force of a process, a phenomenon that determines its character or individual features. At the same time, there is a psychological definition of the concept of "factor", which is interpreted as a structural component of a process, phenomenon, circumstance. If we are given a meaningful aspect if we

transfer it to the personality, we get the structural components of the personality, i.e. its characteristics. A characteristic is a concept that can be collective, singular, positive, negative, concrete, abstract, etc.

As such "concepts" we study reflectivity, social intelligence, empathy, motivation, the level of internality and life-meaning orientations, which, according to the classification of mental phenomena, represent the mental properties of a person. That is, these concepts relate to personality and are therefore called personality characteristics, or personal characteristics. In turn, characteristics relate to the concept of "factor" as its structural components, so we can say that personal characteristics are components of a personal factor, i.e. they make up these factors.

As a result, we can conclude that personal factors are common factors that include various components (in our case, personal characteristics) that contribute to a deeper study of personality in the development of professional reflection. "Reflectivity" is a mental property of a person, i.e. his characteristic. It is also part of the personal factors that form and develop professional reflection, which consciously relies on its "strengths" and minimizes its "weaknesses" in professional activity, and also allows the psyche to identify and fix in itself certain aspects of its qualitative certainty; to represent its features. It is thanks to the differentiation of personal factors that it becomes possible to "access" to each of their individual qualities, mental properties. In addition, the criterion for the successful formation of a specialist is also his motivation, i.e. what motivates him to this type of activity. The level of motivation for professional activity depends on the nature of the motivation of the subject, the motivation of a person to perform work tasks by activating his need-volitional sphere. The formation of professional motivation can be judged by the positive attitude of a person to his profession, the degree of satisfaction with it, as well as by the leading motives for choosing this profession and the professional activity itself.

Success in professional activity is inextricably linked with knowledge, skills, erudition and the ability to think. N. P. Lokalova, for example, indicates that success in the activity of a psychologist directly depends on the level of his thinking processes. But it often happens that gifted students are not successful enough in their professional activities. The profession of a psychologist is associated with the ability to control oneself and competently organize interaction, which is an indispensable quality, since we are talking about the field of activity, implying direct communication with others. This is the main thing in the work of a psychologist. General intelligence is a factor of academic success, which does not always determine high achievements in the future profession. Social intelligence is

formed and developed in the process of learning, communication and with the help of active teaching methods (trainings). It refers to the professionally important qualities of a psychologist, determines the success of professional activity and contributes to success in the profession. In close relationship with the intellectual sphere are personality structures related to value orientations, meaning formation and life-meaning orientations. Life-meaning orientations of a person are the result of a person's relationship to himself and with other people. They are formed at the moment of becoming a student as a subject of his own development, able to realize and analyze his life goals and determine adequate prospects for professional growth. Therefore, professional education for psychology students becomes a reflexive environment, which creates optimal conditions for the formation of meaningful life orientations in them. But their lack of awareness leads to the fact that the process of professionalization becomes spontaneous and unmotivated, and this determines the level of professional reflection reflecting the success of future professional activity. Also, an emotional component is important in the development of a student's professionalism. Understanding another person through emotional feeling into his experiences characterizes the mechanism of empathy. It is impossible to understand another person without entering into some kind of personal relationship with him.

K. Rogers argued that the empathy of a psychologist affects the development of the client's personality, which is a sign of the professionalism of a practical psychologist. Empathy is also a professionally important quality of a psychologist and therefore determines the development of professional reflection in a student. In addition, locus control is an important factor in the development of professional reflection. Two polar types of such localization are possible: external and internal. In the first case, a person believes that the events happening to him are the result of the action of external forces – chance, other people, etc. In the second case, a person interprets

significant events as the result of his own activity. For the effective professional activity of a psychologist, the level of internality is important, which will correlate with the level of meaning in life orientations, and with social intelligence, because these personal factors will determine the behavior of a person both in case of failures and in the field of achievements in professional activity. All of the above personal factors should develop under the influence of special teaching methods, the essence of which is to develop the student's activity not only in the process of academic studies, but also in practical activities during the internship.

Thus, it can be argued that personal factors contribute to the development of professional reflection among students studying in the direction of "Psychology". At the same time, professional reflection determines the positive dynamics of the development of social intelligence, motivation, empathy, the level of subjective control, life orientations. And this interaction, along with the psychological and pedagogical conditions of training, influences the future professional activity of a psychologist, and also ensures its success.

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